

The Hope And The Promise: Minutes of the Presentation

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Abstract

This document presents the transcript of a presentation delivered by three adolescent students — Sanshray Padhy, Ummehani Hussain Kagalwalla, and Saachi Goyal — of Blue Blocks Montessori School, Hyderabad, India. The students chronicle their journey from early Montessori materials through drone-building and patent applications, to the design, fabrication, and near-launch of a CubeSat payload in collaboration with the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) and satellite company TakeMe2Space, under the aegis of ISRO. They also introduce their second satellite project, centred on a deployable fold mechanism aimed at reducing launch costs. The presentation concludes with an invitation to Montessori adolescents worldwide to collaborate on the mission.

Presentation

Ummehani:

- I am Ummehani, I'm 14 years old and I've been going to Blue Blocks Montessori since I was a year old.
- I remember when I was 3 I used to work with the pink tower in the primary environment.
- Slide: Sanshray with pink tower
- Here we can see Sanshray at 3 years old working with the pink tower.
- Today I've got the largest cube of the pink tower and sanshray will tell you why soon.
- Slide: elementary environment
- In elementary we continued using our hands to work with many more Montessori materials.
- Slide: The innovation lab
- We wanted to use our hands to build things, to create things, to construct things. And to enable this need of ours, our founders created a very interesting dedicated space — the innovation lab.
- Any idea we had, we would go to the innovation lab, where we had interesting tools and various materials to work with to build either prototypes or working models.

- We used to also use this space to do our follow-up work in elementary and build 3D models. (recollect if you built any 3D model of the follow up.. like different layers of the earth. Built board games.)
- Seeing our interest and enthusiasm to build things, our founders built another lab.
- Slide: the Drone lab
- The drone lab.
- Why drones?
- Because when we were young we were always fascinated by anything that flew, and it also gave us hands-on experience in aeronautical engineering, mechanical engineering and electronics engineering. When we made our first drones we used materials like ice-cream sticks, fevicol, propellers, motors and accelerometers, and built drones from scratch.
- During our entire journey we were asked one interesting question: "Imagine if your drone could do anything that you want, what would you want your drone to do?" — and this question led to all of us coming up with brilliant ideas.
- I created a medical drone which could help people in medical emergencies. Saachi made a shopping drone which would shop for her, and Sanshray made a borewell drone that would rescue children who fell in borewells.
- Slide: safety drone for his mother
- Look at this interesting and complex drone, which was built by one of our friends when he was 8 years old. He made a safety drone because his mother did late-night shifts, so to bring her home safely he created this unique drone.
- Slide: patents
- Over a period of a few years, there were a hundred-plus interesting drone ideas, and our founders realised that many of them were very unique. They realised some of them were patentable, and they have applied for 5 patents for our drone designs.

Sanshray:

- In 2020 when we applied for those 5 patents I was 10 years old and I was the oldest child at blue blocks.
- As we moved on to adolescence, our ideas grew even larger, much larger than drones. One of the most crazy ideas was building a satellite that could actually go to space. We went up to our founders with this idea, believing that they could make anything possible for us young minds to flourish.
- Slide: space lab

- We collaborated with one of the best colleges of India, the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) to build a space to enable us to build our satellite. Taking our ideas and designs, shaped into reality by IIT, our Space Lab was inaugurated on August 23, 2023, on the exact moment when the moon lander of ISRO's Chandrayan 3 landed on the moon!
- Now we had a space to work in, but it was extremely difficult for our founders to find real experts to guide us in this journey. Then, a miracle happened.
- While we were struggling to get real space and satellite experts out there in the world, it turned out that one of our very own parents led a company called TakeMe2Space, which actually built satellites and sent them to space!
- Imagine what are the odds that one of the few satellite company's founder happens to be our own school parent.
- When our founders spoke to Ronak sir, the ceo of take me to space, ronak sir was not very sure about adolescents capability to be able to build satellite. Pavan sir request him to spend 30 minutes with us to see if we are capable.
- Slide: ronak sir interaction
- And ronak sir, came to visit us in space lab. And back then he just sent his own first satellite. And while he was showing he asked us around 28 questions to check if we understand about space and technology.. like, are magnetic fields scalar or vector? What are wavelengths and frequencies? Why are space stations NOT aerodynamically designed? ..and guess how many questions could we answer.
- All 28 of them.. and he was pretty excited to collaborate with us and help us build this satellite.
- Now we had space, we had expertise and we brain stormed different possible ideas of satellite, which we would like to build.
- We wanted to test all the scientific statistics on earth and space which we were learning in our cambridge program.. like the weather on earth vs weather in space, how things accelerate on the ground vs in the space, how things rotate on earth vs in the space..
- The best way was not to build a huge satellite but a tiny one, and we figured out its called cube sat. this is the size of the satellite we sent.
- When we started working with this sat, I realised it resembled with something I worked with at 3. Show pink tower.
- We got those sensors and started to fabricate
- Slide: working with sensors and board
- We collected the data of these sensors on the ground
- Slide:drone
- We also collected the data of these sensors on the drone to test the statistics in different altitude.
- Slide: hypothesis

- And we all had independent hypothesis of what will be the pattern of statistics in the space for each sensor.
- The satellite was ready: the real challenge was to get the satellite approved by ISRO (Indian Space Research Organisation)
- The satellite had to go through some real rigorous tests. Extreme temperature, vibrations and pressure..
- Slide: Inspace authorisation.
- and you know what..just two weeks before the rocket launch we got our satellite was space ready and got all approvals and it was ready to be mounted on the prestigious rocket of ISRO.
- Slide: press
- When we got the authorisation for our cube sat, the media wanted to know our story.
- Slide:Srihari kota
- Slide: video
- Anomaly: each stage 1 got deployed and there was huge uproar of cheers and applause, and then stage 2, stage 3 and then something happened..
- We were heart broken because we would not get the data we were hoping and yearning so much for.. but when we saw all the 100 scientists of ISRO who worked on a huge satellite for 10 years were having much bigger impact.. seeing them our heart went out for them.
- And then Ronak sir said don't worry we will send the same satellite again.. we received from ISRO team, asking us not to get disheartened, asking us to rebuild and send it again and they extended their design lab and experts to collaborate with us directly.
- And we are Montessori adolescents.. we don't give up.. we have been in Montessori environment since we were one and two year olds and we don't get stopped by breakdowns and failures..
- You know what we are sending the same satellite this October. And once we receive the data from our sensors we would like to share it with the whole of Montessori adolescents community worldwide.

Saachi:

- That is not it.. we are building another satellite, which will also go to space this year. First — why are we doing this?
- Sending things to space is very, very expensive.
- The bigger something is, the more it costs to launch.
- Think about it like luggage on an airplane — you pay more for bigger bags.
- In space, it's the same. Big things cost more.
- So here's our idea:

- What if we could take something BIG... fold it SMALL... launch it cheap... and then open it up in space?
- That's exactly what we're doing.
- Fold small. Launch cheap. Deploy large."
- Let me show you how it works. It's actually simple.
- Step one — the satellite goes up in a rocket.
- Step two — once in space, the lid opens.
- Step three — a fold comes out. This fold is like a big sheet, but compressed very small.
- Step four — a thread burns. This thread was holding the fold closed.
- Step five — the fold opens up. Completely. Automatically.
- The whole thing happens with just one action. We burn one thread, and everything unfolds perfectly.
- One action. Done."
- Now, here's the interesting part.
- This isn't fully solved yet. There are still real engineering challenges.
- Over the next three months, we're working on four problems:
- One — MATERIAL. What material can survive space? It's minus 150 degrees in shadow, plus 150 degrees in sunlight. The material has to fold without cracking. And it has to store energy so it can spring open. What material can do all that?
- Two — FOLD. What fold pattern should we use? Some patterns are already patented — we can't use those. We need to find or invent a fold that works AND isn't owned by someone else.
- Three — RELEASE. How do we hold the fold closed during launch — when the rocket is shaking violently — and then release it gently in space? The same mechanism has to do both: hold tight AND let go.
- Four — ONE SHOT. In space, you get one chance. There's no one to fix it. No second try. How do we make sure it deploys 100% of the time, with just one action?
- These are real problems. And we're working on them."
- This is what we're building.
- We would like to invite adolescents across the world to collaborate with us on the next satellite we are sending.
- Thank you."